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ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Still Your Friend

I remember in high school, we were always side by side,
After class or on weekends, you were my constant guide.
Through struggles in life, we stood strong and true,
No matter the challenge, I had you.

In academics, in dancing, in songs we would sing,
On stage in the theatre, we shared everything.
We trusted each other, a bond tight and real,
A friendship so strong, no one could steal.

We promised forever, come what may,
That nothing in life could pull us away.
But then came college, and paths grew apart,
Still holding our dreams deep in our hearts.

We chose different roads, new goals to pursue,
Believing these choices would help us break through.
We supported each other in all that we do,
Even when distance slowly grew.

Until I saw you less, as time went by,
Just hearing your stories, your lows and your highs.
Your laughter, your tears, I once knew them all,
Now echoes of memories I softly recall.

I heard of your heartaches, the pain you went through,
And though I was distant, I still cared for you.
In silence, I whisper a prayer up above,
That you'll find healing, peace, and love.

Now that we're older, I've come to see,
What friendship truly means to me.
It's not just in dreams we chase side by side,
But in hearts that stay close, though time may divide.

I will always be a friend who prays for you,
No matter how far, no matter what we do.
And all of our memories, both old and new,
Will forever remain my bond with you.